

Comparative *in vitro* antioxidant activity, morphological and phytochemical profiling of traditional crops from Kumaun Himalaya

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Abstract : The phytochemical attributes including proteins, carbohydrates and phenolic content of paddy landraces, millets, pulses, spice and oil yielding crop have been investigated along with the morphological properties of nineteen paddy landraces. *In vitro* antioxidant activity was assessed by ABTS, DPPH radical scavenging method and FRAP assay. The morphological characters varied significantly. *Hordeum vulgare*, *Panicum glaucum*, *Setaria italic* and *Panicum miliaceum* were having much higher protein and carbohydrate contents as compared to most of the studied landraces of paddy. ABTS activity ranged between 0.24 and 354.06 mM/100 AAE while DPPH from 9.00 to 107.90 mM/100 AAE. FRAP assay ranged between 0.016 to 383.20 mM/100 AAE. Badpas rice had the highest ABTS (354.06), DPPH (107.90) and FRAP (383.20) activity. Among millets, *Hordeum vulgare* had the highest antioxidant activity whereas lowest activity was observed for *Panicum miliaceum* and *Setaria italic*. Antioxidant activity of paddy landraces, pulses and oil yielding crop were positively and significantly correlated to the total phenolic content.

Keywords : Phytochemical, phenolics, morphological, Kuloor watershed, antioxidant activity, traditional crops.

Introduction

The traditional food system of the Kuloor watershed is as diverse as its cropping diversity. The food systems in the study area vary amongst societal groups depending on the climatic conditions of the village, location, economic status of a particular family, distance from main road, availability of market and access to modern amenities. All the 15 villages falling within the altitudinal range of 700–2361 m diversity usually exhibit considerable diversity in their food habits. Number of species (landraces) cultivated in the watershed have high nutritional and energy supplement value such as paddy, wheat, maize, ragi, barley, bajra are cultivated along with some lesser known traditional crops. Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a principal food crop providing livelihood security to large section of people all over the world, particularly in Southeast Asia. The Indian Himalayan region represents a wide diversity in agro climatic conditions and rice shows a

wide range of variation¹. Physical qualities of rice affect the marketing values of rice as an agricultural product. The morphological attributes such as width, length and weight of rice kernels determine the physical characteristics of rice grains. There is one report on the characterization of rice landraces from Uttarakhand². All these traditional crops known to comprise of antioxidants, such as flavanoids and other related phenolic compounds, can prevent oxidative degradation of biomolecules such as proteins, DNA and lipids³. There are several investigations on antioxidant potential of phenolic compounds in fruits and vegetables⁴, legumes from India⁵ and China⁶ and commonly consumed cereals, millets, pulses and legumes from India⁷. In the Himalayan Gazetteers of 1882, Atkinson has listed 48 rice varieties⁸, stating that there were thousands of other unidentified varieties; however, correct characterization and antioxidant activity determination is yet to be done. The literature survey reveals

that data on quantification of health beneficial effects of traditional food in Kumaun Himalaya is lacking till to date. Therefore, the aim of the present investigation was to study the *in vitro* antioxidant activity along with morphological and phytochemical characteristics of traditional crops of Kuloor watershed, Kumaun Himalaya.

Results and discussion

Morphological characteristics of paddy landraces :

The morphological attributes i.e. length, width and weight of each rice grain were recorded prior to analysis. The qualitative characters are important for plant description⁹ and mainly influenced by the consumers preference, socioeconomic scenario and natural selection¹⁰. For grain length and width, 25 grains were taken from each landraces whereas grain weight was measured using 25 grains in three replicates of each landrace. Grain weight is a yield attribute¹¹ and weight of 19 rice landraces was found to be ranged from 0.347 ± 0.006 g (Spinger) to 0.712 ± 0.012

g (Laldhan). According to the Portuguese legislation (D.L. 62/2000), the milled rice grain is classified into long (length > 6 mm and length/width ratio of 2–3), medium (length between 5.2 and 6 mm and length/width ratio < 3) and short/round (length ≤ 5.2 mm and length/width ratio < 2.0) dimensions. The smallest grain was found in case of Paktoli (6.81 ± 0.12 mm) and longest for Sunkhali (10.22 ± 0.13 mm). All the grains belong to the large group. The grains of Kashmiri were having minimum (1.54 ± 0.14 mm) whereas Remun (2.44 ± 0.04 mm) had maximum grain width (Table 1). The characteristics of 48 rice varieties from Uttarakhand Himalaya were detected by morphological and biochemical markers. The grains of the selected rice varieties varied significantly in their morphological and biochemical characters suggesting traditional farming system helps in maintaining these attributes².

Phytochemical diversity of diverse landraces :

The protein content among the studied landraces of paddy ranged from 4.46 ± 0.49 (Spinger) to 10.83 ± 0.82

Table 1. Morphological parameters of paddy (*Oryza sativa*) landraces

Sl. No.	Name of the landraces	Width ^z (mm)	Length ^z (mm)	Length/Width	Weight ^z (g)
1.	Nimbari	$1.63^{a,b} \pm 0.03$	$7.20^{d,e} \pm 0.10$	2.71	$0.465^{b,c,d} \pm 0.005$
2.	Laldhan	$2.13^{e,f} \pm 0.04$	$8.32^{i,j} \pm 0.03$	3.91	$0.712^j \pm 0.013$
3.	Sunkhali	$2.20^{f,g} \pm 0.21$	$10.22^k \pm 0.13$	4.65	$0.496^{b,c,d} \pm 0.054$
4.	Laljadi	$2.29^g \pm 0.04$	$7.51^f \pm 0.03$	3.28	$0.703^j \pm 0.050$
5.	Chhoti	$3.05^i \pm 0.04$	$7.25^g \pm 0.03$	2.38	$0.704^j \pm 0.066$
6.	Nandhani	$1.98^{d,e} \pm 0.18$	$7.63^f \pm 0.01$	3.86	$0.583^{f,g} \pm 0.065$
7.	Gadhwari	$1.96^d \pm 0.02$	$7.85^h \pm 0.15$	4.01	$0.430^b \pm 0.020$
8.	Gajadhan	$2.06^{d,e,f} \pm 0.05$	$8.23^i \pm 0.01$	4.00	$0.671^{h,i} \pm 0.028$
9.	Safedhan	$2.09^{d,e,f} \pm 0.01$	$7.53^f \pm 0.04$	3.62	$0.544^f \pm 0.022$
10.	China-4	$1.69^{b,c} \pm 0.04$	$7.66^g \pm 0.00$	4.53	$0.482^{b,c,d,e} \pm 0.033$
11.	Rajadhan	$1.76^{b,c} \pm 0.07$	$7.83^h \pm 0.01$	4.45	$0.582^{f,g} \pm 0.059$
12.	Kashmiri	$1.54^a \pm 0.14$	$6.96^c \pm 0.03$	4.52	$0.431^b \pm 0.022$
13.	Paktoli	$1.77^{b,c} \pm 0.03$	$6.81^b \pm 0.12$	3.85	$0.505^{d,e} \pm 0.018$
14.	Badpas	$2.08^{d,e,f} \pm 0.08$	$6.82^b \pm 0.01$	3.28	$0.638^{g,h} \pm 0.007$
15.	Dalbadal	$1.76^{b,c} \pm 0.07$	$6.60^a \pm 0.16$	3.75	$0.490^{b,c,d,e} \pm 0.050$
16.	Katuri	$1.95^d \pm 0.01$	$7.22^{d,e} \pm 0.01$	3.70	$0.618^{g,h} \pm 0.010$
17.	Kathunia	$1.79^c \pm 0.10$	$10.05^j \pm 0.00$	5.61	$0.531^{d,e,f} \pm 0.032$
18.	Spinger	$2.16^{f,g} \pm 0.02$	$7.11^d \pm 0.01$	3.29	$0.347^a \pm 0.006$
19.	Remun	$2.44^h \pm 0.04$	$7.83^h \pm 0.06$	3.21	$0.451^{b,c} \pm 0.032$
	Range	1.54–2.44	6.81–10.22	4.42	0.347–0.712

^zResults are mean of three replicates \pm standard deviation. Values with different alphabets in a column are significantly different.

(mg/g) (Remun). Among others, Katuri (10.59 mg/g), Safeddhan (10.49 mg/g), Kathunia (10.34 mg/g), Dalbadal (10.80 mg/g), Laljadi (10.00 mg/g), Nimbari (9.32 mg/g) and Nandhani (9.15 mg/g) emerged as a good source of protein. Kathunia (261.96 mg/g), Remun (247.83 mg/g), Nimbari (246.43 mg/g), Rajdhan (243.23 mg/g), Laljadi (231.56 mg/g) and China-4 (222.4 mg/g) landraces of paddy showed high carbohydrate content. Protein content among the Millets ranged from 5.13 ± 0.14 to 20.80 ± 1.42 (mg/g). The highest protein content was recorded in case of Ganera and the lowest in Mandua. Carbohydrate content in five Millets ranged from 713.33 ± 0.29 to 716.33 ± 3.22 . The higher carbohydrate content was present in Mandua and the lowest in Bajra. The significant variation was observed in protein content ($p \leq 0.05$), however, the variation was not significant for carbohydrate content of millet species. Two studied species of pulses varied in their protein content from 5.76 mg/g (Gurunsh) to 46.00 mg/g (Urd). Carbohydrate content for two species ranged between 715.33 ± 1.76 to 719.66 ± 2.96 (mg/g), with highest carbohydrate value for Urd. Significant variation was observed in protein content ($p \leq 0.05$) but same was not true for carbohydrate content among studied pulses. The composition of protein and carbohydrate contents in case of rare spices Bhangjira and oil yielding plant, Til in the watershed has been given in Table.

Diversity in total phenolic contents :

The amount of total phenolic content varied significantly ($p < 0.05$) among the paddy landraces that were ranged between 14.3 ± 0.48 to 31.0 ± 1.06 mg GAE/100 g. Significantly higher level of total phenolic content was recorded in case of landrace Badpas while Kathunia exhibit the lowest phenolic content (Fig. 1). Among the millet species, the total phenolic content varied between 3.36 ± 0.37 to 17.79 ± 0.23 mg GAE/100 g. Significantly higher level (17.79 mg GAE/100 g) of total phenolic content was observed in Mandua while Ganera possessed the lowest phenolic content. As such, a significant variation ($p < 0.05$) in total phenol content in all millets species was observed. The studied pulse species exhibit phenolic range from 1.10 ± 0.13 to 2.63 ± 0.49 mg GAE/100 g and were not significantly different. The studied spices

Fig. 1. Variation in total phenolics in paddy landraces. Values with different alphabets are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$.

Bhangjira had total phenol content of 1.00 ± 0.41 mg GAE/100 g whereas in the oil yielding plant, Til was having 0.50 ± 0.04 mg GAE/100 g. Details of phenolic contents in different studied landraces are presented in Fig. 2. Sreeramulu *et al.*⁷ observed that total phenolic content of cereals/millets were found to be ranged in between 62.35 to 418.34 mg/100 g. They found that rice had the lowest phenolic content (47.64 mg/100 g). In our study, the total phenolic content was very much lower as compared to previous reports^{7,12,13}. The variation in the phenolic content may be due to genetic, environmental factors, extraction procedure and also agro-techniques used for cultivation of different varieties^{14,15}.

Fig. 2. Variation of total phenolics in millets, pulses, spice and oil yielding crop.

Table 2. Protein and carbohydrate content in selected landraces of paddy, millets, pulses, spices and oil yielding plants

Sl. No.	Name of the landraces/species	Botanical name	Protein content ^z (mg/g)	Carbohydrate content ^z (mg/g)
(A) Paddy (Landraces)				
1.	Nimbari	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	9.32 ^{e,f,g,h} ±0.33	246.43 ^{i,j} ±7.93
2.	Laldhan	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	8.71 ^{c,d,e,f} ±0.64	213.40 ^f ±4.97
3.	Sunkhali	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	8.36 ^{b,c,d,e} ±0.53	186.73 ^{b,c} ±6.11
4.	Laljadi	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	10.00 ^{f,g,h,i} ±1.32	231.56 ^h ±1.94
5.	Chhoti	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	7.86 ^{b,c,d} ±0.46	198.60 ^e ±0.64
6.	Nandhani	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	9.15 ^{d,e,f,g} ±0.34	189.93 ^{c,d} ±2.53
7.	Gadhwar	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	8.20 ^{b,c,d,e} ±0.25	187.12 ^b ±1.38
8.	Gajudhan	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	7.72 ^b ±0.84	162.00 ^a ±1.76
9.	Safeddhan	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	10.49 ^{g,h,i} ±0.89	275.06 ^l ±1.27
10.	China-4	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	4.48 ^a ±0.35	222.40 ^g ±2.51
11.	Rajdhan	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	7.29 ^b ±0.40	243.23 ⁱ ±0.68
12.	Kashmiri	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	5.79 ^a ±0.41	221.41 ^g ±0.62
13.	Paktoli	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	4.50 ^a ±0.49	185.36 ^{b,c} ±0.33
14.	Badpas	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	5.62 ^a ±0.53	181.43 ^b ±0.82
15.	Dalbadal	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	10.80 ⁱ ±1.47	214.60 ^f ±0.74
16.	Katuri	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	10.59 ^{h,i} ±0.83	199.03 ^e ±2.67
17.	Kathunia	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	10.34 ^{g,h,i} ±0.40	261.96 ^k ±2.05
18.	Spinger	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	4.46 ^a ±0.49	195.13 ^{d,e} ±2.11
19.	Remun	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	10.83 ⁱ ±0.82	247.83 ^j ±2.52
	Range		4.46–20.80	162.00–275.06
(B) Millets				
1.	Mandua	<i>Eleusine coracana</i> (Brummitt and Powell)	5.13 ^a ±0.14	716.33 ^o ±3.22
2.	Jaun	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> L.	9.93 ^{f,g,h,i} ±0.98	713.33 ^o ±0.29
3.	Bajra	<i>Panicum glaucum</i> L.	12.20 ^j ±0.39	713.33 ^o ±6.66
4.	Kauni	<i>Setaria italic</i> (L.)	15.53 ^k ±0.49	715.00 ^o ±4.58
5.	Ganera	<i>Panicum miliaceum</i> L.	20.80 ^l ±1.42	714.33 ^o ±4.94
	Range		5.13–20.80	713.33–716.33
(C) Pulses				
1.	Gurunsh	<i>Vigna trilobata</i> (L.) Verdc.	5.76 ^a ±0.78	715.33 ^o ±2.23
2.	Urd (Black)	<i>Vigna radiate</i> (L.) R. Wilczek.	46.00 ^o ±1.32	719.66 ^o ±3.53
(D) Spice				
1.	Bhangjira	<i>Perilla frutescens</i> extracts (PPE)	27.40 ^m ±0.74	690.33 ^m ±4.85
(E) Oil yielding				
1.	Til	<i>Sesamum orientale</i> L.	42.00 ⁿ ±0.50	705.33 ⁿ ±4.16

^zResults are mean of three replicates ± standard deviation. Values with different alphabets in a column are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$.

Antioxidant activity :

Antioxidant activity measured by various *in vitro* as-

says for millets, pulses, spices and oil yielding species are given in Table 3. It is well known that, the phenolic com-

Table 3. Phytochemical analysis of paddy, millets, pulses, spices and oil yielding plants

Sl. No.	Name of the landraces/ species	ABTS ^z (mM/100 AAE)	DPPH ^z (mM/100 AAE)	FRAP ^z (mM/100 AAE)
(A) Paddy				
1.	Nimbari	47.67 ^h ± 1.38	63.80 ^{g,h} ± 1.79	65.10 ^k ± 0.17
2.	Laldhan	43.62 ^g ± 0.94	97.20 ⁿ ± 0.73	118.50 ^p ± 0.48
3.	Sunkhali	34.20 ^e ± 2.31	50.10 ^e ± 0.71	26.00 ^d ± 1.00
4.	Laljadi	48.44 ^h ± 0.86	65.40 ^{h,i} ± 0.89	86.30 ^o ± 1.31
5.	Chhoti	57.73 ⁱ ± 3.02	70.90 ^k ± 0.71	86.70 ^o ± 1.07
6.	Nandhani	96.02 ⁿ ± 2.92	73.00 ^k ± 0.50	76.30 ^m ± 0.94
7.	Gadwar	48.85 ^h ± 1.35	63.10 ^g ± 0.31	58.70 ⁱ ± 1.87
8.	Gajudhan	96.60 ⁿ ± 1.54	76.80 ^l ± 0.66	80.20 ⁿ ± 1.06
9.	Safeddhan	102.68 ^o ± 1.27	104.50 ^o ± 4.11	343.40 ^t ± 2.16
10.	China-4	51.88 ⁱ ± 0.86	82.40 ^m ± 0.36	62.70 ^j ± 0.26
11.	Rajdhan	58.41 ^{j,k} ± 1.26	57.50 ^f ± 0.70	57.80 ⁱ ± 0.90
12.	Kashmiri	67.09 ^m ± 1.11	47.10 ^d ± 0.31	131.60 ^q ± 1.08
13.	Paktoli	60.15 ⁱ ± 0.13	28.00 ^b ± 0.59	67.30 ⁱ ± 0.84
14.	Badpas	354.06 ^p ± 1.79	107.90 ^p ± 1.26	383.20 ^s ± 0.72
15.	Dalbadal	50.95 ⁱ ± 1.77	57.60 ^f ± 0.59	37.70 ^f ± 1.66
16.	Katuri	39.57 ^f ± 0.58	67.60 ^{i,j} ± 2.70	32.00 ^e ± 1.32
17.	Kathunia	33.57 ^e ± 1.03	68.60 ^k ± 2.57	20.00 ^c ± 0.78
18.	Spinger	44.50 ^g ± 0.74	66.10 ⁱ ± 1.15	41.60 ^g ± 0.66
19.	Remun	28.66 ^d ± 0.71	77.10 ^l ± 1.80	50.40 ^h ± 1.15
	Range	28.66–384.06	28.00–107.90	20.00–383.20
(B) Millets				
1.	Mandua	0.67 ^a ± 0.03	10.36 ^a ± 0.38	0.016 ^a ± 0.001
2.	Jaun	7.10 ^c ± 0.10	15.45 ^b ± 0.46	7.056 ^b ± 0.087
3.	Bajra	5.76 ^{b,c} ± 0.24	13.71 ^b ± 0.41	6.036 ^b ± 0.956
4.	Kauni	0.24 ^a ± 0.02	9.76 ^a ± 0.42	0.039 ^a ± 0.001
5.	Ganera	0.29 ^a ± 0.02	9.00 ^a ± 0.44	0.021 ^a ± 0.001
	Range	0.24–7.10	9.00–15.45	0.016–7.056
(C) Pulses				
1.	Gurunsh	0.89 ^a ± 0.05	10.02 ^a ± 0.09	0.256 ^a ± 0.027
2.	Urd (Black)	0.80 ^a ± 0.05	9.47 ^a ± 0.51	0.177 ^a ± 0.022
(D) Spice				
1.	Bhangjira	3.73 ^b ± 0.12	10.84 ^a ± 1.50	1.740 ^a ± 0.115
(E) Oil yielding				
1.	Til	0.89 ^a ± 0.01	9.60 ^a ± 0.66	1.550 ^a ± 0.047

^zResults are mean of three replicates ± standard deviation. Values with different alphabets in a column are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$.

pounds contribute to grain quality and nutritional value by modifying colour, taste, aroma, and flavour, and also provide beneficial health effects. The antioxidant activity assay was carried out to assess the ability of the medicinal extracts to scavenge free radicals. Study of antioxidant activity using three different *in vitro* assay i.e. ABTS,

DPPH, FRAP showed considerable variation across studied rice landraces. Results revealed significant variation ($p \leq 0.05$) in total antioxidant activity measured by ABTS method. Antioxidant activity measured by ABTS method ranged from 28.66 ± 0.71 to 354.06 ± 1.79 mM/100 AAE. Highest antioxidant activity was found in Badpas

(354.06 ± 1.79 mM/100 AAE) while the lowest was found in Remun (28.66 ± 0.77 mM/100 AAE). Total antioxidant activity using DPPH method ranged between 28.00 ± 0.59 to 107.90 ± 1.26 mM/100 AAE, with highest value for Badpas and lowest for Paktoli. Similarly, total antioxidant activity measured by the FRAP method, ranged between 383.20 ± 0.72 to 20.00 ± 0.78 mM/100 AAE. Landrace, Badpas showed the highest FRAP antioxidant activity while Kathunia exhibited the lowest activity. Among 5 species of millets, antioxidant activity measured by ABTS method ranged from 7.10 ± 0.10 to 0.24 ± 0.02 (mM/100 AAE), while Jaun exhibited maximum activity and Kauni the minimum. Total antioxidant activity using DPPH method ranged between 9.00 ± 0.44 to 15.45 ± 0.46 mM/100 AAE. Jaun exhibited the highest antioxidant activity and Ganera, the lowest. Similarly, total antioxidant activity measured by the FRAP method, ranged between 0.016 ± 0.001 to 7.056 ± 0.087 mM/100 AAE. Jaun showed the highest antioxidant activity and Mandua the lowest. Results revealed significant variation ($p \leq 0.05$) in total antioxidant capacity measured by FRAP and DPPH method in all millets species. The spices Bhangjira had ABTS (3.73 ± 0.12 mM/100 AAE), DPPH (10.84 ± 1.54 mM/100 AAE) and FRAP (1.740 ± 0.115 mM/100 AAE) while in the oil yielding plant, Til, ABTS, DPPH and FRAP were, 0.89 ± 0.01 mM/100 AAE, 9.60 ± 0.66 mM/100 AAE and 1.550 ± 0.047 mM/100 AAE respectively. Total phenolics, flavonoid contents and antioxidant capacity from a wide collection of rice germplasm were measured. Their relations to grain, colour, grain size and 100 grain weight were also investigated¹⁶. Highly significant genotypic differences were observed in total phenolics, flavonoid contents and ABTS. Phenolic acids and antioxidant activities of 12 Thai rice varieties consisting of pigmented rice and normal rice was determined¹⁶.

Correlation between phenolic content and antioxidant activity :

Correlation between phenolic content and antioxidant activity of various tested crops is shown in Table 4. Significant correlation was observed between phenolic content of paddy landraces and ABTS ($r^2 = 0.748^{**}$), DPPH ($r^2 = 0.572^{**}$) and FRAP ($r^2 = 0.779^{**}$). Phenolic con-

Table 4. Correlations between phenolic content and antioxidant activity of different traditional crops

Traditional crops	ABTS	DPPH	FRAP
Paddy	0.748 ^b	0.572 ^b	0.779 ^b
Millets	0.021	0.131	-0.035
Pulses	0.892 ^a	0.912 ^a	0.719
Spice	0.500	-0.485	-0.676
Oil yielding	0.359	1.000 ^a	0.700

^aCorrelation is significant at the $p \leq 0.01$ level.

^bCorrelation is significant at the $p \leq 0.05$ level.

tent of millets and spices showed no significant correlation with antioxidant activity. Significant positive correlation was observed between pulses phenolic content and ABTS ($r^2 = 0.892^*$) and DPPH activity ($r^2 = 0.912^*$) while good correlation was observed between oil yielding Til phenolics and DPPH free radical scavenging activity ($r^2 = 1.000^*$). The correlation results of millets and spices suggested that the antioxidant components other than phenolic compounds may contribute to the antioxidant activity¹⁷. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on morphological, phytochemical characteristics and antioxidant activity of traditional crops of Kumaun Himalaya.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents :

All reagents used in the experiment were of analytical grade. Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, sodium carbonate, aluminium chloride (AlCl₃) and gallic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA); 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH); 2,2-azinobis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonate) (ABTS), potassium persulfate and methanol used were purchased from Fluka Chemie (Buchs, Switzerland). Acetonitrile, L-ascorbic acid and ferric chloride (FeCl₃.6H₂O) were purchased from Fisher Scientific Co. (Fair Lawn, NJ, USA).

Collection of crop grains :

Grains of paddy (*Oryza sativa* L.), millets (Mandua; *Eleusine coracana*. (Brummitt and Powell), Jaun; *Hordeum vulgare* L., Bajra; *Panicum glaucum* L., Kauni; *Setaria italic* (L.), and Ganera; *Panicum miliaceum* (L.),

pulses (Gurunsh; *Vigna trilobata* (L.) Verdc. and Urd; *Vigna radiate* (L.) R. Wilczek.), spices (Bhangjira; *Perrilla frutescens*) extracts (PPE)) and oil producing crop (Til; *Sesamum orientale* L.) varieties were collected from various ecological zones. All the grains were air dried at 25 °C and ground using kitchen grinder to get fine flour and passed through a 72 µm sieve.

Morphological characterization :

The morphological attributes i.e. length, width and weight of selected paddy landraces were recorded prior to analysis. In case of paddy, grain length and width of 25 grains was analyzed using Absolute Digimetric Vernier Callipers (Mitutoya CD-6" CS, Japan). The grain weight of 25 grains in three replicates was measured using weighing balance (Afcoset ER-182A, India).

Estimation of protein :

Protein content in all samples was determined by Bradford assay¹⁸. Grains (50 mg each) of paddy, millets, pulses, spices and oil producing plant variety in triplicate were randomly sampled and crushed using mortar and pestle in 500 µL protein extraction buffer containing 60 mM Tris-HCl (pH 6.8), 25% glycerol, 0.1% bromophenol blue, 10% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and 14.4 mM 2-mercaptoethanol. The samples were vortexed thoroughly and the proteins were extracted at room temperature for 20 min. The samples were denatured at the water temperature 100 °C for 5 min. These were again mixed properly by vortexing for 2–3 min and then centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 12 min at room temperature. Supernatant were transferred to a new 1.5 ml eppendroff tubes. To 10 µL of extract, 90 µL of H₂O was added followed by 100 µL phosphate buffer saline and 5 mL binding dye and absorbance was taken at 545 nm. The protein content of each extract was determined from the standard curve based on Bovine Serum Albumin. The content was expressed in mg/g.

Estimation of carbohydrate content :

The estimation of carbohydrate was done by anthrone reagent method¹⁹. 100 mg of paddy, millets, pulses, spices and oil producing plant variety sample was taken in boiling tube and 5 ml of 2.5 N HCl was added. The samples

were hydrolyzed by keeping it in a boiling water bath for three hours and then cooling at room temperature. Sodium carbonate was added in the sample to neutralize it. Final volume was prepared to 100 ml and centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 15 min at room temperature. The supernatant was collected and 0.5 and 1 ml aliquots were taken for analysis. Standards were prepared by taking 0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1 ml of the working standard. Final volume was prepared up to 1 mL in all tubes including the sample tubes by adding distilled water. Then 4 mL of anthrone reagent was added and heated for eight minutes in a boiling water bath. The samples were cooled rapidly and the absorbance was measured at 630 nm. A standard graph was prepared by plotting concentration of the standard on X axis versus absorbance on the Y axis and the content was expressed in mg/g.

Extract preparation :

Dried grain powder (100 mg) was extracted in 10 ml of 80% (v/v) methanol solvent + 1 N HCl in a conical flask and kept at room temperature for 1 h with continuous shaking. After thorough mixing, the flask was allowed to stand in a water bath at 55 °C for one hour and kept at room temperature overnight with continuous shaking. Thereafter, the solution was sonicated for 10 min using an Ultrasonicator. The resultant suspension was filtered using Whatman No. 44 filter paper in to a 100 ml capacity volumetric flask. Extract was further centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 min and supernatant was collected. This supernatant was stored at 4 °C until the analysis of phenol and antioxidant activity was carried out. For quantification of phenolic composition, the resultant suspension was filtered using 0.45 µM pore size filter and stored at -4 °C.

Estimation of total phenolic content :

Total phenolic content in the methanolic extract of paddy, millets, pulses, spices and oil producing crop varieties was determined by Folin-Ciocalteu's calorimetric method²⁰. Methanolic extract (0.5 ml) diluted with distilled water (4.5 ml) was mixed with Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent (0.5 ml) and allowed to stand for reaction for 5 min. This mixture was neutralized by 7% sodium carbon-

ate (5 ml) and kept in dark at room temperature for 90 min. The absorbance of resultant blue color was measured at 765 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Quantification of total phenolic content was done on the basis of standard curve of gallic acid prepared in 80% (v/v) methanol as mg of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per 100 g of sample (mg GAE/100 g).

Determination of ABTS radical scavenging activity :

Total antioxidant activity was measured by the ABTS (2,2'-azinobis 3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) radical scavenging method²¹. ABTS (7.0 μ M) and potassium per sulfate (2.45 μ M) was added in to an amber coloured bottle and kept for 16–18 h at room temperature in the dark. The ABTS solution was diluted with 80% (v/v) ethanol till an absorbance of 0.700 ± 0.05 at 734 nm is obtained. For sample analysis ABTS cation solution (3.90 ml) was added to 0.1 ml of supernatant sample and mixed thoroughly and allowed to stand for six minutes in dark at 23 °C temperature. The absorbance was recorded at 734 nm on the UV-Vis spectrophotometer (U-2001, Hitachi, Japan). Samples were diluted 80% (v/v) in different solvent to obtain the concentration. Results were expressed in mM ascorbic acid equivalent (AAE) per 100 g dry weight of powdered grains of paddy, millets, pulses, spices and oil producing crop variety.

Estimation of DPPH radical scavenging activity :

This method given by Brand-William, Cuvelier and Berset²² is based on scavenging of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl radical (DPPH). 400 μ M DPPH was dissolved in pure 80% ethanol. DPPH cation (DPPH) (3.0 ml) was mixed with sample extract (1 ml) and kept in dark at room temperature for 20 min. Reduction in the absorbance at 520 nm was recorded by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Results were expressed in mM ascorbic acid equivalent (AAE) per 100 g dry weight of powdered grains of paddy, millets, pulses, spices and oil producing crop variety.

Estimation FRAP :

Ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay is a technique to determine the total antioxidant power interpreted as the reducing capability. The FRAP assay was

first given by Benzie and Strain²³ and Faria *et al.*²⁴ with some modifications. A mixture of 300 mm acetate buffer (pH 3.6) (i.e. 3.1 g of sodium acetate and 16 mL glacial acetic per liter); 10 mM TPTZ (2,4,6-tri-2-pyridyl-1,3,5-triazin) in 40 mM HCl (1 vol.) and 20 mM ferric chloride (1 vol.) was made to prepare the FRAP reagents. The mixture was pre warmed at 37 °C for 8 min. Absorbance was taken at 593 nm UV-Vis spectrophotometer for quantification. A blank sample was prepared by ascorbic acid and results were expressed in mm ascorbic acid equivalent (AAE) per 100 g dry weight of powdered grain of paddy, millets, pulses, spices and oil producing crop variety.

Statistical analysis :

All the estimations of morphological, phytochemical attributes and antioxidant activity were conducted in three replicates. The value for each sample was calculated as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Significant difference among means was tested by one way ANOVA (Duncan's test) using SPSS 16.0. Correlation between phenolic content and the antioxidant activity was performed by Pearson's correlation test using SPSS 16.0. Significance level of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Conclusion

The study clearly reveals that a number of species/landraces cultivated in the watershed had higher nutritional and energy supplement value. Remun, Katuri, Safeddhan, Kathunia and Dalbadal among paddy landraces were the important source of protein. Whereas, for carbohydrate content Kathunia, Remun, Nimbari and Rajdhan emerged as good source. Among others, many of the millets, which are now not used as preferred food, showed much better nutritional potential as compared to cereals. Jaun, Bajra, Kauni and Ganera, all were having much higher protein and carbohydrate contents as compared to most of the studied landraces of paddy. The amount of total phenolic content varied significantly among the paddy landraces with Badpas having the highest value. Among millets the highest value was observed for Mandua. Study of antioxidant activity using three different *in vitro* assays, i.e. ABTS, DPPH and FRAP, showed considerable

variation across studied landraces of paddy. All three assays, however, revealed that landrace Badpas exhibits maximum antioxidant activities. Among millets, Jaun had the highest antioxidant activity. Many of the landraces possessed significantly higher antioxidant potential. This study demonstrated the potential of lesser known traditional crops for cultivation.

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